

USING MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH**Sotvoldiyeva Muattarxon Ikromjon qizi**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10275667>**Abstract :**

The use of contemporary techniques in English instruction is examined in this article. The primary objective of teaching foreign languages to preschoolers is to help them acquire useful English language skills in addition to improving their speech and vocabulary.

Keywords: English language, modern methods, speech, foreign languages, information, technologies, education system, learning process, methods of teaching, globalization.

Introduction

In daily life, people are choosing to speak English more and more. The global impact of English-language movies, music, and popular culture has contributed to its widespread use. People often want to engage with and understand these cultural products. English is a dominant language on the internet and various social media platforms. People interact, share, and communicate online in English, influencing its prevalence.

English facilitates global networking and connections. People communicate with professionals, colleagues, and friends from different parts of the world, and English often serves as the common language. English is often the medium of instruction in higher education, making it necessary for many students to learn and use English to succeed in their academic pursuits. It is useful to know English language such as a vast amount of information and resources are available in English. This includes books, scientific research, online content, and media. People who speak English have easier access to these valuable resources. English is widely spoken in the tourism industry. Knowing English can facilitate travel and make interactions with people in different countries easier. English language is important in today's modern life, so new methods should be used in teaching English. In doing so, teachers explore interactive methods and curriculum, and help students learn through new technologies and websites.

Individualized Approach: Each student should receive an individualized approach based on their learning and developmental requirements and needs. The teacher should guide the students with appropriate approach methods.

Moral support: Teachers should support students morally and solve moral problems and issues while teaching.

Teaching Support for Research: Teachers lead research so that they can seek out innovations in their field and conduct research. This helps to organize the educational process better.

Interactivity: Teachers should support interactive methods in teaching lessons, such as making teaching interactive through textbooks, add-ons, video conferencing, websites, and apps.

International Collaboration: Teachers can seek opportunities to collaborate and benefit from other teachers through international networking.

Knowledge of new technologies and teaching tools: Teachers learn about new technologies, applications and teaching tools, as well as best practices for online teaching. Creativity: Teachers need to support students' creativity in mastering learning materials, learning new teaching methods, and learning.

The main findings and results

In today's world of modern technology, one of the modern teaching methods is online teaching. Online learning has several advantages:

An online learning site or application allows students and teachers to access learning from anywhere in the world.

Students can choose their own study schedule based on their own consumption and personal convenience at their convenience.

Online learning gives students access to texts, videos, programs, audio materials, and additional learning resources.

Online learning helps learner flexibility and learning mastery. They can choose and implement their own educational program and methods.

Online tutors can provide a programmatic approach and support to students. They benefit students through additional tips and approaches.

With online learning, students get more personalized tutoring, volunteer tutoring, and interactivity than any other method.

An online learning site or application accepts students from anywhere in the world, and the geographical location of teachers is also not limited.

In online education, teaching becomes easier with the benefits of today's technology, such as interactive tutorials, video conferencing, counseling, and other facilities. Knowing which language students want to study and giving them the opportunity to choose subjects that interest them.

Using supplementary materials, videos, add-ons, and games to make language teaching lessons fun and interactive.

Create a curriculum that outlines the steps students will take in learning another language. Additional resources, such as, books, audio materials, and online resources, can help students learn other languages.

Creating opportunities for students to learn other languages by speaking with a group, watching cartoons and movies, and getting to know students from other countries.

Conducting language teaching through a spiritual approach, trying to make the learning of additional languages dependent on human comfort and beliefs.

Teachers should be experts in teaching other languages and be able to help students find inspiration.

Be able to support students with learning methods that suit them, explaining their individual needs.

These techniques can help make learning another language easy and fun for students. Teacher support training can be useful. Teacher support training can be useful.

Interactive methods and programs: Teachers explore interactive methods and programs to help students learn through new technologies and websites.

Individual disorders: Each student should be treated individually according to his studies, requirements, and needs. The teacher should guide the students with appropriate testing methods. Moral support: Teachers should provide moral support to students and solve moral problems and issues during the teaching process.

O's learning support: Teachers manage the volume so they can search and review their news. This helps to organize the educational process better.

Interactivity: Teachers should support interactive methods in teaching their lessons, such as making teaching interactive through textbooks, add-ons, video conferencing, websites, and apps.

International Collaboration: Teachers can seek to collaborate and benefit from other teachers through an international network.

Knowledge of new technologies and teaching: Learn how teachers learn to learn new technologies, applications, and learning, and learn about good practices in online teaching. Creation: Teachers need to be supported in mastering educational materials, learning new teaching methods, and providing learning opportunities.

These definitions will be useful for teachers to teach students well and help them in the learning process. Preschoolers can be more motivated to learn English when an interactive whiteboard is used in the classroom. These technologies enable youngsters to actively participate in their education, greatly boost their motivation to learn, foster creativity, and shape their personalities. Expanding the possibilities for information delivery, interactive learning's accessibility, and methodical content presentation aid in teaching kids while taking into consideration their unique characteristics. Interactive whiteboard classes include children actively participating in visual exercises in addition to watching and listening to audio and video content. Utilizing animation capabilities, object selection, movement, and color-based selection enables you to process information through both visual and audible channels. Youngsters can focus their attention on the.

Conclusion

One of the most significant ways to teach English is through sign language. Children develop a fondness for special educators when they see them with kindness and a soft smile from the educator. Children may move freely and enjoy learning a foreign language with the use of gestures. We establish a stimulating environment for language learning. Children should enjoy the game by putting themselves in new situations, but interactive play should not be mistaken for role-playing. This is an important issue to consider. The latter resembles a theatrical production more. Setting up an interactive game with preschoolers is crucial because it allows the kids to experience social interaction in a way that is meaningful to them. These kinds of games allow children to practice speaking with their teachers and peers as well as to participate in coordinated group cognitive exercises that promote social growth.

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